

THE ESSENCE OF CUSTOMS PAYMENTS AND THE NECESSITY OF THEIR APPLICATION

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Annotation.

This article discusses the analysis of customs payments collected by the customs authorities. Based on the research results, scientific proposals and practical recommendations are given.

Key words: customs payments, import duty, excise tax, value added tax, customs fees.

One of the current issues of our country is optimizing the system of regulating foreign trade through customs payments, taking into account advanced foreign experiences, international principles and norms, and improving the mechanisms of its collection.

The amount of duty and tax rates plays an important role in the formation of the country's budget income, as well as influencing the development of the country's foreign trade.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the strategy of "Uzbekistan - 2030"" was adopted. According to this Decree, "Ensuring the well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth" was defined as one of the priorities. In the 46th goal of this direction entitled "Ensuring fiscal stability and effective management of state obligations" - "Ensure that the consolidated budget deficit is less than 4 percent of gross domestic product (GDP) in 2024 and less than 3 percent in the coming years." [1]

Customs payments on imported goods make up 98 percent of the total customs payments collected in our country, and taxes make up 80-84 percent. In order to promote the export of goods in our country, based on the current regulatory documents, customs fees are not collected during customs clearance of goods for export (except for customs fees). [4]

The following scholars expressed their opinions on the meaning of customs payments.

D.A.Slepov and E.V.Chuykov said that customs payments are calculated by the employees of the customs authorities and are a source of income of the federal budget. [2]

Scientists I.V. Gomon, M.V. Neparko, N.I. Reshetov showed that customs payments are the basis for forming the federal budget. Customs payments include customs duty, value added and excise taxes, and customs duties. [3]

In general, customs payments are duties, taxes, and customs fees determined by law to be collected by customs authorities when goods are transported across the customs border by participants in foreign economic activity. They are an important condition for the implementation of customs regulation.

In recent years, a number of reforms have been carried out regarding the calculation, collection and transfer of customs payments to the state budget, and the legal framework for their collection is being improved.

As a result of the creation of facilities for the participants of foreign economic activity in this direction, the amount of customs fees collected is also increasing year by year. Analysis shows that this indicator increased by 10.1 times in 2013-2022.

The increase in customs payments was influenced by the main factors such as: the increase in the volume of imported goods, the improvement of the determination of the customs value of goods, the change in the rates of customs payments, the change in the freely exchangeable exchange rate, the effective use of the automated information system in the customs sector, and the improvement of the regulatory and legal framework in the customs sector.

The share of customs fees in the state budget revenue in Uzbekistan is also increasing year by year. This indicator was 17.6 percent in 2013, and by 2022 it was 20.8 percent. During this period, this indicator increased by 3.2 percent. We can see that this indicator was high in 2013-2014 and 2020-2022 and low in 2015-2019 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. In 2013-2022, the dynamics of the share of customs fees in the state budget revenue (in percent)

Source: Prepared by the author based on information from the Customs

Committee

One hundred percent of customs payments are transferred to the revenue part of the state budget in addition to customs fees.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022, the total customs payments included: value added tax 84.1%, import customs duty 12.5%, excise tax 0.8%, other payments 2.6%. In 2015, these figures were 54.5, 24.9, 17.3 and 3.3 percent, respectively.

Table 1

The composition of customs payments transferred to the State budget by customs authorities in 2015-2022 (percentage)

№	Types of customs payments	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1.	Import customs duty	24,9	25,8	22,5	16,1	13,5	14,3	16,1	12,5
2.	Value added tax	54,5	54,1	60,4	74,5	78,5	79,8	83,6	84,1
3.	Excise tax	17,3	17,2	14,5	4,6	4,6	3,7	0,1	0,8
4.	Customs fees and other payments	3,3	2,9	2,6	4,5	3,4	2,2	0,2	2,6
Total		100,0							

Source. Author's development based on information from the Customs Committee.

In the above years, we can see that the weight of value-added tax in the structure of customs payments transferred to the State budget has increased, but on the contrary, the weight of import customs duty, excise tax, customs fees and other payments has decreased. This is directly related to the processes of carrying out reforms on the application of customs payments, that is, the reason for this is that they are optimizing the rates of customs payments and increasing the measures to increase the effectiveness of the benefits provided by them.

The analysis of the total amount of customs payments and benefits transferred to the state budget by the customs authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2013-2022 shows that the amount of customs payments calculated in these years increased by 5.1 times, the amount of benefits granted by them increased by 3.7 times, and the amount of customs fees transferred to the state budget increased by 5.1 times. increased by 10.1 times. Also, in 2013,

the share of customs payments transferred to the state budget was 22.8% of total customs payments, and in 2022, this indicator was 44.9%, and this indicator increased by 22.1% in these years.

Based on the above, the following are proposed to improve the fiscal activity of the customs service:

- effective analysis of factors affecting the collection of customs payments and improvement of logical control in preventing additional calculated customs payments;

- improvement of the mechanism of calculation and collection of customs payments;

- review and optimize customs payment benefits and improve their control mechanisms.

In conclusion, the effective organization of customs payments serves the development of our country's economy and the increase in the volume of foreign trade, as well as ensuring the stability of the state budget.

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